

DIVINFOOD

Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food

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Guidelines to assess food and raw material quality along different approaches

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Executive summary

This deliverable provides guidelines for assessing the quality of food and raw materials along different approaches, with a focus on diverse and healthy plant-based products co-produced within living labs (LLs) as part of the DIVINFOOD project.

This document integrates nutritional, sensory and safety aspects into operational tools designed for use by R&D teams, SMEs and/or innovation actors to ensure that diverse plant-based recipes meet rigorous scientific and commercial standards.

These guidelines are based on the systematisation of DIVINFOOD partners' experience with legume- and cereal-based matrices, across various living labs and analytical platforms, with consumer co-creation to support the effective selection and optimisation of plant-based food products.

We hope that these guidelines will facilitate the implementation of scalable and scientifically robust quality assessment approaches, which can be adopted by research partners, SMEs and innovation actors throughout the value chain, for the co-creation of plant-based foods that are nutritionally adequate, sensorially acceptable and safe.

1. General introduction on GUIDELINES in DIVINFOOD

The European DIVINFOOD project is a research and innovation project developed in collaboration with stakeholders and designed to be useful to them. It aims to facilitate and increase the use of Neglected and Underutilised Crops (NUCs) in food value chains, which requires guidelines at different stages to better implement and optimise the use of these little-known species or varieties, which lack references and benchmarks. Thus, a set of complementary DIVINFOOD deliverables presents Guidelines, related to the assessment of food and raw material quality along different approaches (D2.4), to the implementation of farming systems enhancing NUCs performances and Ecosystem Services delivery (D3.4), to the implementation of novel breeding techniques and approaches (D4.4), and to the set up territorial networks to manage agrobiodiversity (D5.5).

These deliverables in guidelines format are intended to facilitate the use of NUCs by stakeholders across Europe, from their cultivation to the organisation of cooperation networks in the territories. They present good practices and points to watch out for in language that is concise and accessible to those directly involved. The work carried out in DIVINFOOD provides use cases and data from which partners can take a step back to advise others on the implementation of these activities, with a view to spreading them across Europe and as a source of inspiration for actors not yet involved in these activities.

This deliverable D2.4 is part of this set of deliverables and presents the Guidelines to assess NUC food and raw material quality along different approaches, ranging from laboratory analysis to participatory evaluation with consumers. It was completed one month behind schedule in order to provide a summary table of the guidelines for each approach.

2. What is food and raw material quality?

Food product quality encompasses sensory appeal (taste, texture, look, smell), nutritional value, safety (no contaminants/pathogens, spoilage microorganisms control), and increasingly, ethical/sustainable production (origin, process, branding). It's a mix of objective characteristics and subjective consumer perception. Quality is maintained by adhering to specifications, using management systems, and meeting consumer demands for health, convenience, and ethical sourcing (Petrescu et al., 2020).

For plant-based systems, quality must be considered both at raw material level (e.g. legumes, cereals) and at product level (e.g. formulated foods), recognising that processing can improve or deteriorate these attributes (e.g. excess processing). There is a need for standardised guidelines that can accommodate similarities and differences across products and regions with varying geographic and socio-economic contexts (Filip et al., 2025).

We can define different dimensions in food quality, such as nutritional/health beneficial, organoleptic/sensorial, and safety/regulatory.

2.1 Nutritional and health beneficial quality

This dimension reflects the contribution of a food or ingredient to human health, including, nutrient composition (protein, including amino acid profile, fat, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals) and components with recognised health effects such as dietary fibre and bioactive compounds (flavonoids, polyphenols, and antioxidant activity). In plant-based systems, attention must also be given to anti-nutritional factors (e.g. alkaloids, B-ODAP) and how processing may affect all the above composition (Meier et al., 2021). Also, the assessment of in-vitro digestibility of proteins to estimate the fraction potentially available for absorption after gastrointestinal digestion (bioavailability) is an important section of this quality dimension.

2.2 Organoleptic or sensorial quality

Organoleptic quality refers to food product attributes perceived by the senses, including appearance, colour, odour, flavour and texture, which collectively drive consumer liking and acceptance. For plant-based formulations, sensory quality is often the main barrier to repeat purchase (Mihafu et al., 2020; Imtiyaz et al., 2021).

2.3 Safety and regulatory quality

Safety and regulatory quality ensures that raw materials and food products are free from unacceptable biological, chemical and physical hazards and comply with EU and national legal requirements for composition, contaminants, allergens, microbiological criteria and labelling (Meier et al., 2021; Uddin et al., 2026). The legislative background Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs lays down the rules to which the Food Business Operator (FBO) must comply the microbiological criteria for undesirable microorganisms, hygiene

indicator bacteria, spoilage species and pathogen bacteria. Food business operators are responsible for the safety of the products they place on the market. They must take the necessary measures, throughout their production, processing and distribution, to ensure that these products comply with microbiological criteria.

References

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- Mihafu et al. (2020) Implication of sensory evaluation and quality assessment in food product development: A review. *Curr. Res. Nutr. Food. Sci.* 8(3). doi:10.12944/CRNFSJ.8.3.03.
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- Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 of 15 November 2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs.
- Uddin et al. (2026) Chapter 35 - Safety and regulatory frameworks for unconventional food sources. In: *Dietary, Sensory and Gastronomic Applications* (Sarkar T, Smaoui S, Eds). Academic Press. pp719-745.

3. Why to assess food and raw material quality?

Systematic quality assessment underpins safe, accepted and nutritionally meaningful plant-based products and reduces failure risk during co-creation and market introduction. It enables partners to benchmark existing foods, define improvement targets and document the impact of innovations across living labs.

3.1 Consumer-driven motivations

Consumer expectations increasingly combine health, sustainability and convenience, with growing attention to ingredient lists and origin. For plant-based foods, trust is fragile if products appear highly processed, do not meet taste expectations, or fail to deliver the promised nutritional benefits.

Scepticism toward ultra-processed plant-based products encourages simpler recipes while maintaining safety and quality. Consistent quality assessments and documentation contribute to perceived credibility of plant-based innovations and support communication with stakeholders. Nutrient profiling and clear nutrition information are therefore critical to align product composition with expectations and public-health recommendations.

3.2 Processor-driven motivations

For SMEs and other processors, robust safety assessment and routine quality control reduces risks and supports strategic positioning in rapidly evolving plant-based markets. Also demonstrated nutritional and sensory quality, combined with documented safety and sustainability practices, enables credible differentiation of plant-based products.

4. How to assess quality?

A multi-criteria framework was established among the DIVINFOOD partners, integrating nutritional, sensorial, and safety dimensions. Methods were selected according to the food product category, project resources and the regulatory context, while aiming for harmonisation across partners.

4.1 Methods for assessing nutritional quality developed in the DIVINFOOD project

Protein, fat, fibre have been quantified in DIVINFOOD for different legumes (common bean and grass pea) seed flours using **spectroscopic methods** (Fourier-transformed ATR), after the optimisation of specific prediction models. Targeted quantification of anti-nutrients (e.g. ODAP in grass pea, alkaloids in lupin) and cereal gluten quality analysis were performed using **spectrophotometric or chromatographic techniques**. Chromatographic techniques were also used for the assessment of total phenolic content and antioxidant capacity as first indicators of bioactive potential. **In-vitro digestion models** applied to selected products or raw materials were used to assess protein and starch digestibility, and possible release of bioactive compounds.

4.2 Methods for assessing safety quality developed in the DIVINFOOD project

Microbiological safety assessment approaches have been developed under DIVINFOOD, by Aerial, third party of ACTIA. A **microbiological assessment** of the microbiological hazards potentially associated with the raw materials (cereals, legumes) and the applied mild process (thermal treatment, fermentation, drying, soaking...) was carried out. The relevant pathogen bacteria and spoilage, hygiene microorganisms to screen in the plant-based recipes of plant origin have been listed. **Experimentations were drawn up** (protocols, sampling plan, microbiological analysis, pH, water activity measurements) **to validate the microbial quality** of the food products recipes that have been validated from a nutritional and sensory perspective.

4.3 Methods for assessing sensorial quality developed in the DIVINFOOD project

DIVINFOOD sensorial quality assessment approaches varied from laboratory-based descriptive analysis to community-based tastings in living labs. Examples were the **use of trained panels to generate sensory profiles** of new food products and reference products, based on agreed lexicons for appearance, odour, flavour and texture, or the development of **consumer and community-based tests**, using standardised **hedonic scales, CATA and pivot tests**, with harmonised questionnaires and minimal common metrics (e.g. 9-point liking, key CATA attributes) or the implementation of **in-home or community settings** (schools, restaurants, households) for context-relevant evaluation, ensuring basic control of instructions and serving conditions. In some contexts, instrumental texture analysis to quantify rheological and mechanical properties linked to mouthfeel and process ability were performed.

5. Good practices to implement quality assessment

Each quality assessment method should be supported by well-defined guidelines that describe its implementation procedures and critical points of attention. Providing clear instructions on how to organise and execute different assessment methods is essential to ensure reproducibility and comparability across studies. These guidelines serve as a practical reference for others to replicate and apply similar evaluation frameworks. In this section, we present a set of guidelines compiled from the collective experience of DIVINFOOD partners engaged in food and raw material quality assessments.

The Table 1 below presents the methods for which guidelines are provided in this deliverable, applied to various NUCs (as raw material or food products) and quality dimensions. Possible users of guidelines are specified for each method, ranging from lab experts to innovation actors. In the following section, each method is introduced by a table outlining the DIVINFOOD partner who implemented the method, the technique, the possible users, the purpose, the cost, and the key warnings. For each method, scientific and technical references are provided.

Quality dimension	Methods guided in the deliverable	Possible users of the method
Nutritional quality	Spectroscopy FTIR-ATR	Trained user with no specific expertise (when a prediction model already exists) Small-scale companies
	Spectroscopy NIR	Trained user with no specific expertise (when a prediction model already exists) Breeding companies
	High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)	Lab experts Big and small-scale companies
	In-vitro digestion models	Lab experts
Safety quality	Microbiological analysis	Small-scale food producers Farm advisors
Sensorial quality	Sensorial profile with trained panel (CATA methodology)	Big and small-scale companies
	Consumer tastings	Innovation actor- Trained staff
	Consumer evaluation with cooking and tasting at home	Innovation actor- Trained staff
	Recipe creation by chefs	Innovation actor

Table 1. Methods of quality assessment developed in DIVINFOOD and guided in this deliverable, with possible users

5.1 Guidelines for nutritional quality assessment

5.1.1 Good practices for the use of spectroscopy to assess nutritional quality and anti-nutritional compounds in legumes

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
UNL	FTIR-ATR (Fourier Transformed Infrared-Attenuated Reflectance)	Trained user with no specific expertise (when a prediction model already exists ¹) Small-scale companies	Fast non-destructive functional group identification Define accurate prediction models of nutritional and anti-nutritional parameters	€	Ensure sample variability Ensure reproducibility (technical replicates) Check instrument performance Keep the ATR crystal clean between measurements

The assessment of legume's nutritional quality and anti-nutritional composition by spectroscopy involves three good practices:

- i)** Selection of appropriate spectroscopy techniques (e.g., Nuclear Magnetic Resonance-NMR, Near-infrared-NIR, Fourier Transformed Infrared-FTIR);
- ii)** Standardisation of sample preparation and when not available yet,
- iii)** development of accurate chemometric models which articulate spectroscopy data with measurements obtained by traditional methods (wet chemistry).

i) Under the scope of the DIVINFOOD project, Fourier Transformed Infrared-Attenuated Reflectance (FTIR-ATR) was broadly used, since a rapid, sensitive, non-destructive method was required for functional group identification and accurate prediction models of major nutrients and anti-nutrients. With such purpose characteristic spectral bands, were associated with the data determined by wet chemistry using multivariate statistical tools (BenchChem Technical Support Team, 2025).

ii) For the samples' homogeneity and to reduce the matrix effects previously to the FTIR-ATR analysis, the seed samples were dried and ground to a particle size of 0.8mm. The flour samples were kept at room temperature, ideally in a desiccator for the moisture content control. To enhance the analysis sensitivity, a small amount of the flour sample was put directly onto the ATR crystal without touching or scratching the crystal with the spoon.

Prior to the analysis, a background spectrum of the clean ATR crystal should run to subtract atmospheric and instrumental interferences. Perform also blank runs by pressing the piston against the clean ATR crystal, between different samples to detect potential carryover contamination. Cross-contamination between samples was avoided by rinsing the crystal with Milli-Q® water, followed by acetone, and then dried with soft tissue. This procedure was followed between each analysis. The equipment was checked according to supplier's tests (e.g., signal, ATR, and resolution).

¹ Almost anyone can use an NIR or FTIR instrument to analyse seeds or flour, provided it has already been calibrated, and thus automatically obtain a quantification of the desired characteristic. The fact that it is calibrated means that a predictive model has already been developed to convert the spectral data into the quantitative content of the compound of interest. If such a model does not exist, someone with the necessary expertise must develop it, and this task requires specific skills.

iii) To define validated chemometric models several steps were considered:

- Data representativeness (data variability was checked, and influent outliers removed)
- Spectral pre-processing was conducted to normalize data and increase the signal-to-noise ratio
- The quality of wet-chemistry data was evaluated by checking the error between technical triplicates and the variation in the control samples.
- Calibration models were developed using different methods (e.g., Principal Component Analysis PCA, Partial Least Square PLS regression, Support Vector Machine SVM regression, Artificial Neural Network ANN, clustering analysis).
- Separation of the dataset into three independent groups: a training, a validation and a testing (independent external dataset), 70:15:15. The training dataset is used to develop the model. The validation dataset allows an unbiased evaluation of the model's performance and to fine-tune the model's parameters. The testing dataset is used to test the model's performance with unseen data after the model has been fully trained.
- Select meaningful spectral regions by testing all spectra and different regions. The meaningful regions should generate models with better performance.
- Control the performance of the models by checking the R2 of calibration and validation datasets: High R2 in calibration but low R2 in validation indicate data overfitting.

RMSEP (Root Mean Square Error of Prediction), the cross-validated RMSECV and the RPD (Residual Predictive Deviation) calculated as the ratio between SD of the reference wet chemistry data and the RMSEP, should be also calculated. RPD higher than 2.5 indicates a model with good predictive ability (Sileoni et al., 2011; Zaccarelli et al., 2025).

References

BenchChem Technical Support Team 2025. A comparative guide to the synthesis and spectroscopic validation of 2-Indanone. https://pdf.benchchem.com/58/A_Comparative_Guide_to_the_Synthesis_and_Spectroscopic_Validation_of_2_Indanone.pdf
 Sileoni et al. (2011) Internal and external validation strategies for the evaluation of long-term effects in NIR calibration models. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 59:1541–1547. doi:10.1021/jf104439x
 Zaccarelli et al. (2025) Improving quality monitoring in Medicago sativa biorefinery using handheld near-infrared spectroscopy and machine learning, *Appl. Food Res.* 5:101151. doi:10.1016/j.afres.2025.101151.

5.1.2 Good practices for the quantification of alkaloids in lupin using spectroscopic approaches

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
CREA-ZA	Near-infrared spectroscopy (NIR)	Trained user with no specific expertise (when a prediction model already exists) Breeding companies	Fast non-destructive screening of lupin seeds and flour for feed and food and to support selection of low-alkaloids varieties/lines	€	Condition samples at the same temperature: 40°C was used in this application. Standardise grinding procedure (30 Hz for 40 seconds) and instruments to guarantee the same granulometry of the flour. Avoid heating the flour. Adapt NIR acquisition setup to guarantee accurate mean spectra and allowing the processing of a large number of samples per day. Defat flour prior chemical analysis not to negatively affect the performances of the chromatographic columns.

For studies of selection for low alkaloid content, white lupin landraces (ecotypes of the CREA-ZA world collection), cultivars (spring-type and winter-type germplasm) and cross derivatives (Recombinant Inbred Lines from crosses) were gathered. All samples were conditioned at 40°C and analysed with a NIRFlex 500 spectrometer (Büchi Italia, Cornaredo, Italy).

Two applications were developed: 1) grains were recorded using the tablet adapter of the measurement cell averaging the spectra of 10 random individual seeds per sample; 2) seeds were milled (using a MM400 Mixer Mill by Retsch GmbH & Co., Germany) at 30 Hz and flours were NIRS scanned by means of a vial adapter of the measurement cell, averaging 3 repetitions of the same samples.

Flours samples were chemically analysed as official references (Barzaghi et al., 2025) in the development of the NIR calibrations for total quinolizidine alkaloids, considering 2 biological replicates (the procedure by Boschini et al., 2008 based on GC-MS was followed with minor modifications). Prior chemical analysis, flour samples were defatted with hexane.

By associating spectroscopic and chemical data, a first discrimination of high-alkaloid (bitter-seeded) vs. roughly low-alkaloid (relatively sweet-seeded) white lupins was performed using a Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis (PLSDA). Calibration PLSDA models were calculated using the PLS Toolbox software (ver. 9.3, Eigenvector Research, Inc., Manson, WA, USA) for: a) broadly sweet-seed breeding lines; b) landrace accessions; c) a combination of these materials. Samples were divided in a set of calibration (75%) and a set of validation (25%) using the Duplex algorithm. Spectra were pre-processed using Savitzky-Golay first derivative.

The PLSDA analysis was successful in distinguishing between bitter and sweet flours, with less than 1% of misclassification (Barzaghi et al., 2025). In general, NIRS spectra obtained by whole seeds gave results negatively influenced by light scattering effects due to surface roughness and variability in seed size.

NIRS predictions for total alkaloids were developed by Partial Least Square Regression (PLSR) models calculated on the average spectra using the R package Chemometrics version 1.4.4. The analysis adopted the repeated double cross-validation method (Filzmoser et al., 2009), which is recommended to identify the optimal number of latent variables and obtain a more reliable estimation of the prediction performance. The double cross-validation was repeated 100 times with different random splits into test and calibration sets. The prediction ability was assessed using R² and RPD statistics (Williams, 2014).

Poor results (i.e. RMSEP too high and R² in cross validation too low) were obtained from NIRS regression models to precisely quantify the alkaloid content if below or above the severe threshold of 200 mg/kg of alkaloids, compulsory for lupin grain utilization as a food (Barzaghi et al., 2025). As observed for PLSDA, NIRS spectra of whole seeds gave results negatively influenced by light scattering effects due to surface roughness and variability in seed size.

NIRS technology is usually best suited for major and abundant compounds. However, it can contribute to a very useful pipeline for low alkaloids white lupin selection.

References

Barzaghi et al. (2025) Quinolizidine alkaloid composition of white lupin landraces and breeding lines, and Near-Infrared Spectroscopy-based discrimination of low-alkaloid material. *Plants*, 14: 3327.
 Boschini et al. (2008) Quinolizidine alkaloids in seeds of lupin genotypes of different origins. *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 56: 3657–3663.
 Filzmoser et al. (2009) Repeated double cross validation. *J. Chemom.* 23: 160–171.
 Williams (2014) The RPD Statistic: A Tutorial Note. *NIR News* 25: 22–26.

5.1.3 Good practices for the use of chromatographic approaches to analyse bioactive compounds

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
UNL	High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)	Lab experts Big and small-scale companies	Chromatographic profile; non-volatile compounds identification and quantification	€€	Be careful with the preparation of the mobile phase solutions (e.g., Use solvents HPLC-grade; Ultrasonicate the eluents prior to the analysis and purge the eluent lines before use) Control the room temperature Always filter the extracts prior to the analysis Check system suitability (baseline, peak symmetry, retention time and peak area of control standards and/or control sample) Program the gradient method to include an equilibration-time between analysis to avoid peak drift

For an accurate analysis of bioactive compounds by liquid chromatography some important good practices were followed:

The phenolic compound extracts were protected from light and heat, being preserved at -20°C prior to the analysis. The extracts were filtered using a CA 0.20µm filter to prevent contaminations and column clogging. When possible, freeze-thaw cycles were minimized by dividing the extract into different eppendorfs, to prevent compounds' loss. The extracts were prepared in triplicate to understand potential extraction variability.

Prior to the HPLC analysis the eluent solutions were freshly prepared in enough volume to allow the analysis of all vials included in the sequence. The sequence included blanks of solvent (to check for potential carryover issues) and control mixtures with compounds of known concentration. The elution gradient program stabilized prior to the analysis and a washing analysis step was planned by the end of the sequence. The autosampler and column temperatures were checked and controlled during the analysis. For quantification purposes standard compounds were analysed under the same conditions of samples including at least 5 concentration levels with equidistant points. Linearity of the calibration curves was confirmed with $R^2 > 0.99$. For quantification purposes the compounds concentration in the extract were within the tested range of concentrations, above the limit of quantification (LOQ). For the triplicates an error lower than 15% was considered acceptable. Consistent integration method was applied for samples comparison (e.g., baseline, and delimiters). The identification of compounds was made by comparison with the retention time and UV-Visible typical spectra of standards analysed under the same conditions.

5.1.4 Good practices for the use of chromatographic approaches to analyse protein composition of wheat

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
INRAE	High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)	Lab experts	Chromatographic profile; protein identification and quantification	€€	To prepare SE-HPLC extracts, start with ground samples having a particle size <0.5 mm. For RP-HPLC extracts, extraction can be performed on coarsely crushed half-grains. Be careful with the preparation of the mobile phase solutions (e.g., Use solvents HPLC-grade) Control the room temperature (SE-HPLC) and column temperature (50°C, RP-HPLC)

Objective: To analyse protein composition of wheat grains grown under different cropping systems in order to evaluate bread making or pasta making potential.

Methodology: Size Exclusion-High Performance Chromatography (SE-HPLC) and Reverse-Phase High performance Chromatography (RP-HPLC).

- Size exclusion High Performance Liquid Chromatography (SE-HPLC)

Kernels will be ground into flour. Proteins will be extracted using a phosphate-SDS (sodium dodecyl sulphate) buffer from flour samples according to the method described by Morel et al. (2000), with some modifications. SDS-soluble proteins will be recovered after centrifugation, while insoluble fraction (Fi) will be released using sonication.

The proteins from the two extracts will be separated on a TSK G4000SWxl 7.8 mm x30.0 cm column (Tosoh Bioscience) and eluted with phosphate-SDS buffer. The first chromatogram will be divided into 5 fractions: F1 to F5 according to Morel et al (2000). Fractions F1 and F2 respectively comprise the largest and smallest glutenin macropolymers. F3 comprises mainly ω gliadins, F4 comprises $\alpha/\beta + \gamma$ gliadins and F5 comprises water and salt soluble protein together with traces of gliadins. The area under the second chromatogram will be used to measure the insoluble protein fraction (Fi). The gliadin/glutenin ratio will be estimated from the ratio of F4 to (F1+F2+Fi). The total protein content of flour will be estimated from the total SE-HPLC area as indicated by Morel et al (2001).

- Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC)

Albumin-Globulin, gliadin and glutenin extracts will be prepared from flour samples according to Wieser and Seilmeier (1998) with modifications. Extracts will be separated at 50°C on a C18 RP-HPLC column (250 x 2.1 mm, 5 μ m, 300 Å) with the following elution system: (A) 0.1 % (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid (TFA), (B) 0.08 % TFA (v/v) in acetonitrile. The gradient will be as follow: Albumins plus globulins extract: 0 min 20% B, 20 min 60% B, 23 min 90% B, 28 min 90% B, 32 min 20% B, 42 min 20% B. Gliadin and glutenin extracts: 0 min 28% B, 30 min 56% B, 33 min 90% B, 38 min 90% B, 41 min 28% B, 51 min 28% B. Elution flow rate will be maintained at 0.2 mL/min and UV detection will be recorded at 210 nm.

Requirements: ca 10-100 g wheat grain or flour

Shipping information on:

- Wheat species/variety
- Drying after harvest
- Cropping system
- Labelling of samples should be described

References

Morel et al. (2000) Effects of temperature, sonication time, and power settings on size distribution and extractability of total wheat flour proteins as determined by size-exclusion high-performance liquid chromatography. *Cereal Chem.* 77:685-691.

Morel et al. (2001) Reliable estimates of gliadin, total and unextractable glutenin polymers and total protein content, from single SE-HPLC analysis of total wheat flour protein extract. in: *Wheat gluten*. (Shewry PR & Tatham AS eds.) Royal Society of Chemistry, Cambridge, UK. Pages 140-148.

Wieser and Seilmeier (1998) The influence of nitrogen fertilisation on quantities and proportions of different protein types in wheat flour. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 76:49-55.

5.1.5 Good practices for the use of chromatographic approaches to analyse protein composition of cereal products (bread, pasta)

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
INRAE	High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)	Lab experts	Chromatographic profile; protein quantification	€€	To prepare SE-HPLC extracts, start with ground samples having a particle size <0.5 mm. Be careful with the preparation of the mobile phase solutions (e.g., Use solvents HPLC-grade) Control the room temperature (SE-HPLC)

Objective: To analyse the solubility of proteins from breads and pasta made using different technological processes to assess their effect on gluten cohesion.

Methodology: Size Exclusion-High Performance Chromatography (SE-HPLC).

From freeze-dried bread samples or freeze-dried cooked pasta, proteins will be extracted using a phosphate-SDS (sodium dodecyl sulphate) buffer according to the method described by Morel et al (2000), with some modifications. SDS-soluble proteins will be recovered after centrifugation, while insoluble fraction will be released using reduction and sonication. Indeed, due to mechanical and thermal treatments applied to the dough, the pellet will be resuspended in SDS-sodium phosphate buffer containing 20 mM dithioerythritol (DTE) before being sonicated. The new supernatant containing DTE-soluble proteins will be stored until analysis. A residual pellet still remained containing all the unextracted proteins.

Areas under the two chromatograms will be calculated to obtain SDS-soluble and DTE-soluble protein proportions. The non-extracted protein fraction will be calculated by subtracting the sum of SDS-soluble protein content and DTE-extracted protein content from the Kjeldahl total protein content.

Requirements: 2 slices of bread (1 cm thick) without crust – 50 g dry pasta.

Shipping information on:

- Wheat species/variety
- Technological process
- Labelling of samples should be described

Handling:

- Pasta should be cooked at their optimal cooking time (AACC Method 66-50.01).
- Ideally, bread slices and cooked pasta should be freeze-dried before protein extraction. Alternatively, bread and pasta samples can be dried at 50°C and stored in airtight plastic bags.
- Freeze-dried samples should be ground before protein extraction.

References

Belahcen et al. (2022) Physicochemical and sensorial characterization of artisanal pasta from the Occitanie region in France. *Foods* 11(20): 3208.
 Cereals & Grains Association. Pasta and noodle cooking quality - firmness. In *AACC Approved Methods of Analysis*, 11th ed.; Method 66-50.01; Cereals & Grains Association: St. Paul, MN, USA.

5.1.6 Good practices for measuring protein digestibility measurement from bread and pasta samples

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
INRAE	Enzymatic digestion Total protein content determination	Lab experts	Protein digestibility of cereal products	€€	Use ground samples having a particle size <0.5 mm Control the enzymatic reaction temperature (incubator +37°C)

Objective: To evaluate the protein digestibility of bread or pasta samples to assess the strength of the gluten network and the influence of manufacturing processes on its structure.

Methodology: Reagents from the Protein digestibility assay kit (PDCAAS, Neogen, Auchincruive, UK) will be used for the digestion steps. The undigested protein content will be determined by total protein quantification using Kjeldahl method.

Before measurement, the bread slices and cooked pasta (at optimal cooking time) will be freeze-dried and ground. Using the Megazyme method, the proteins in the ground sample are first digested by pepsin (1 hour) and then by a mixture of trypsin and chymotrypsin (4 hours). After the reaction has stopped, the sample is centrifuged and the protein content of the pellet is measured (undigested proteins).

Requirements: ca two slices of bread without crust or 50 g of dry pasta.

Shipping information on:

- Wheat variety
- Breadmaking or pasta making process
- Labelling of samples should be described

Handling:

- Pasta should be cooked at their optimal cooking time (AACC Method 66-50.01).
- Ideally, bread slices and cooked pasta should be freeze-dried before protein digestion. Alternatively, bread and cooked pasta samples can be dried at 50°C and stored in airtight plastic bags.
- Freeze-dried samples should be ground before protein extraction.

References

Belahcen et al. (2022) Physicochemical and sensorial characterization of artisanal pasta from the Occitanie region in France. *Foods* 11(20): 3208.
 Cereals & Grains Association. Pasta and noodle cooking quality - firmness. In *AACC Approved Methods of Analysis*, 11th ed.; Method 66-50.01; Cereals & Grains Association: St. Paul, MN, USA.

5.2 Guidelines for safety quality assessment

5.2.1 Good practices for the microbiological safety studies and experimentations

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
AERIAL (Actia third party)	Microbiological analysis of raw critical materials Checking Traceability Routine microbiological analysis of the plant-based products Checking the microbiological criteria: microbiological shelf-life studies	Small-scale food producers Associations of small-scale food producers Farm advisors	Raw material (cereals, legumes) can be a source of contamination by pathogenic bacteria (e.g <i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>), spoilage flora (e.g <i>Bacillus</i> spp, lactic flora...) and hygiene indicator bacteria (<i>E. coli</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ...). Mild processed plant-based products need to follow the European legislation concerning microbiological criteria requirements.	€	Cereal and legume production: apply good hygiene practices, do not use animal-based fertilisers Raw material storage conditions: apply good hygiene practices: clean, dry area, adequate temperature, using clean equipment Trained farmer and small food producers On site: good hygiene practices, H.A.C.C.P Keep under control the mild processing: a manufacturing diagram, clear threshold parameters. Healthy plant-based food: recipes description, packaging or not need to be determined; clear labelling: “use-by-date” (temperature/duration), “best-before” (temperature/duration), description of use by the consumer (directly, reheating, cooking, ...)

Food businesses that produce ready-to-eat foods capable of supporting the growth of undesirable microorganisms, and which undergo / or do not undergo heat treatment or other processes capable of eliminating them during production, must be able to demonstrate that their products will remain compliant with the requirements of Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 throughout the shelf-life of the product.

References

Koutsoumanis et al. (2020) Guidance on date marking and related food information: part 1 (date marking). *EFSA European Food Safety Authority Panel on Biological Hazards EFSA Journal* 18(12):6306, 74. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6306>
 EC Regulation No 2073/2005 of 15 November 2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs and its revisions.

Awad et al. (2024) Climate changes and food-borne pathogens: the impact on human health and mitigation strategy. *Climatic Change* 177: 92. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-024-03748-9>

Barka (2024) Effects of climate change on plant pathogens and host-pathogen interactions. *Crop and Environment* 3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crope.2024.05.003>.

Codex CXC 1-1969 (2022) General principles of food hygiene. https://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius/shproxy/en/?lnk=1&url=https%253A%252F%252Fworkspace.fao.org%252Fsites%252Fcodex%252FStandards%252FCXC%2B1-1969%252FCXC_001e.pdf

French national network ACTIA QUALIMA "Control of the microbiological quality of food" provide methodologies and tools. <https://www.actia-asso.eu/projets/qualima-2/>

5.3 Guidelines for sensory quality assessment

5.3.1 Good practices for applying the CATA methodology for sensorial profile analysis combined with a consumer panel overall liking test

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
UNL	Sensorial profile with trained panel	Big and small-scale companies	Objective sensory assessment of innovative food products	€€	At least 10 trained assessors with experience in dynamic sensory methods and with training for the type of products Evaluation should be conducted in controlled sensory booths ensuring uniform testing conditions

The sensory evaluation studies were conducted to assess the acceptance and sensory profile of the fermented grass pea-based products. The tests were carried out using a panel of expert tasters which apply dynamic sensory profiling through Temporal Check-All-That-Apply (TCATA) (Castura et al., 2016). This method enables an objective sensory assessment that integrates and describes the evolution of sensory attributes throughout the entire oral trajectory during consumption. Also, a naïve panel of consumers evaluate the samples in terms of liking and perception.

The trained panel should consist of at least 10 assessors with experience in dynamic sensory methods and with training for the type of products. The panel development included recruitment, pre-selection, selection tests, specific attribute training, technical training and product-specific training. Assessors were required to meet regulatory criteria related to sensory acuity and response reliability. To support panel training, lists of sensory attributes were developed based on previous descriptive sensory studies with the matrices under study (fermented grass pea). At the end of the first session, a brief discussion session was held to discuss the suitability of the attribute lists.

The objective of the TCATA methodology was identify all applicable attributes at each moment during the tasting, selecting new sensations as they arise. For the dynamic evaluation, the sensory attributes were perceived over an evaluation period of 60 seconds, followed by an eight second fading interval. Each sample was evaluated in triplicate to ensure reproducibility. A good indicator of data quality is a high degree of agreement among tasters and that all of them have high repeatability.

For the consumer evaluation a nine-point hedonic scale (Peryam and Pilgrim, 1957) was used by the consumers who were invited to describe their positive and negative perceptions. Consumers evaluated each sample in a monadic and sequential way, with a balanced order of presentation across participants. This evaluation was conducted in controlled sensory booths ensuring uniform

testing conditions, and with at least 100 consumers. Each booth was equipped with paper napkins, a glass of water, and crackers to allow tasters to cleanse their palate between samples.

References

Castura JC, Antúnez L, Giménez A, Ares G (2016) Temporal check-all-that-apply (TCATA): A novel dynamic method for characterizing products. *Food Quality and Preference*, 47:79–90. Doi: 10.1016/j.foodqual.2015.06.017
 Peryam DR, Pilgrim FJ (1957) Hedonic scale method of measuring food preferences. *Food Technol* 11(S1):9-14.

5.3.2 Good practices for implementing other sensory methods

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
EI Purpan (INRAE)	Sensory methods with a trained or untrained panel	Lab experts Big and small-scale companies	Appreciation, description or discrimination of products	€	Specify the objective of the analysis and the available resources Comply with ethical requirements Use a Latin square design to avoid any bias in the product sample Apply the appropriate method depending on the objective

The first step is to clearly define the objectives of the study and the reasons for using sensory analysis. It is essential to specify whether the aim is **appreciation, description, or discrimination** among the samples. The second step is to determine the available resources with respect to the project timeline, including whether a trained or untrained panel is available and whether consumer feedback is required. Based on the objectives and available means, the appropriate sensory method can then be selected.

For the panel, ethical requirements must be addressed, including data protection, an explanation of the project, confirmation that participants have no food allergies or medical contraindications, and their informed consent to participate.

To limit bias during sample evaluation, each sample should be coded with three-digit random numbers, and a **Latin Square design** should be used to balance serving order. Furthermore, before the tasting session, panellists must refrain from smoking, drinking coffee, chewing gum, or wearing perfume, as these factors may affect sensory perception.

If a rapid description of a set of products is needed, a **12-person panel**, untrained but experienced with other products, can perform a **Ranking Descriptive Analysis (RDA)**. This method consists of ranking a set of products (typically 6–8) according to a list of descriptors selected by the panel. It is an alternative to **Flash Profiling**.

Two sessions are required. The first session is used to establish a consensus list of the most relevant attributes for discriminating the samples. In the second session, all samples are presented simultaneously, and panellists rank the products according to each selected descriptor. The sensory data are analysed using Friedman tests to compare samples on each attribute and Generalised Procrustes Analysis (GPA) to obtain a consensus sensory configuration.

If the goal is to obtain a product description, the **Pivot Profile** method can be used. With a trained panel, 12 panellists are sufficient, whereas with an untrained panel, at least **60 participants** are required. In this method, each sample is compared to a reference product (the “pivot”), selected beforehand among all products as the most central in terms of colour, texture, and taste. Participants then evaluate the samples according to different criteria (appearance, in mouth

texture, aroma, and taste) and generate free attributes expressed as “more” or “less” than the pivot. Negative wording and hedonic comments must be avoided.

If the objective is appreciation, a **hedonic test** is appropriate. A ranking test may be carried out according to **NF ISO 8587** to classify 6–8 samples based on hedonic preference. Samples are presented simultaneously to each panellist, who ranks them from most preferred (rank 1) to least preferred. The sensory data are analysed using **Friedman tests** to compare samples.

5.3.3 Good practices in implementing consumer tastings at city events

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
DVF	Consumer tastings	Innovation actor- Trained staff	Overall liking assessment of innovative food products	€	<p>To ensure reproducibility and comparability across studies, tastings should be implemented using harmonized and transparent procedures</p> <p>Participation should be voluntary, anonymous and based on informed consent.</p> <p>The event context (type of event and duration) should be documented, as it may influence consumer responses</p> <p>Simple and standardised preparation methods are recommended to minimize variability and highlight intrinsic product characteristics</p> <p>It is recommended using a nine-point hedonic scale suitable for non-trained consumers</p> <p>Cooking times need to be adapted to each pea variety to reach a comparable softness</p>

Consumer tastings conducted at city events are a practical approach to assessing consumer acceptance of food products under realistic consumption conditions. To ensure reproducibility and comparability across studies, tastings should be implemented using harmonised and transparent procedures, as outlined below.

Consumer tastings should be organised at public events with high visitor flow and relevance to food or sustainability. The tasting setup must be clearly visible and easily accessible. Participation should be voluntary, anonymous and based on informed consent. The event context (type of event and duration) should be documented, as it may influence consumer responses.

Tested products must be clearly defined and aligned with project objectives (e.g. species, variety or processing level). Simple and standardised preparation methods are recommended to minimise variability and highlight intrinsic product characteristics. All samples should be prepared under identical conditions and served in appropriate portions. Product origin and preparation details should be recorded.

Tastings should be facilitated by trained staff providing neutral and standardised instructions, also being able to answer any questions about the tasting and/or questionnaire. Participants should receive a brief explanation of the tasting procedure and evaluation method. Samples should be presented consistently, with water available for palate cleansing.

Overall liking should be assessed using some sort of questionnaire (paper-based or digital). It is recommended using a nine-point hedonic scale suitable for non-trained consumers. Hedonic

scales are easy to understand and quick to apply, which is essential in public or time-limited settings such as city events and food festivals.

The nine-point hedonic scale is widely used in sensory and consumer science, allowing results to be compared across studies, products and contexts. Its standardised structure supports reproducibility and statistical robustness while minimising respondent fatigue. Furthermore, hedonic scales generate quantitative data that can be readily combined with demographic and behavioural information, enabling analysis of preference patterns across consumer groups. For these reasons, hedonic scaling represents a reliable, efficient and internationally recognised method for assessing consumer acceptance in food tasting studies.

Short open-ended comments and/or free word association may be included to support interpretation of hedonic data. Following the tasting, a concise questionnaire may be used to collect key demographic and lifestyle information relevant to food choice and acceptance.

Ethical requirements, including data protection, must be respected. Personally identifiable data should be avoided unless strictly necessary. The number of participants, any deviations from the protocol and practical constraints should be documented. These measures ensure data quality and enable replication and comparison across studies and locations.

5.3.4 Good practices in implementing consumer tastings at public events

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
SLU	Consumer tastings	Trained staff	Overall liking assessment of innovative food products	€	<p>It is recommended using a nine-point hedonic scale suitable for non-trained consumers</p> <p>Cooking times need to be adapted to each pea variety to reach a comparable softness</p> <p>If the tasting is performed at a multilingual event one needs to be aware of risks of misunderstandings or misinterpretations of questions and answers</p> <p>The evaluation and comparison of different samples, the order in which participants taste different samples should therefore be randomised</p>

Within DIVINFOOD, SLU collaborated with DVF in the organisation of a public tasting of four pea varieties (three landraces and one modern variety) at the Copenhagen plant food festival in November 2025. The tasting followed the description above, and we here provide guidelines and recommendations adapted to cooked but otherwise un-processed peas, based on experiences and learnings from this evaluation.

The tested pea varieties were three Swedish pea landraces and a modern Swedish yellow pea variety. Cooking times were adapted to each pea variety to reach a comparable softness.

At the event, samples were served cold in paper cups. Mentimeter.com was used for data collection, allowing participants to access the questions through their smartphones via a QR code. The initial slide entailed an introduction with instructions, followed by background questions about demographic and consumer habits. In the next step of the questionnaire, the participants were asked to rate their liking of taste, texture, appearance, and overall liking of each pea sample

according to the hedonic scale from 1 to 9 (1 = extremely bad; 9 = extremely good). For each variety, this was followed by a question to share one word (with the possibility to add more if wanted) describing the taste.

The online procedure for the tasting surveys enables the compilation of relatively large data sets (in the range 50 – 100 participants or more) and statistical analysis data. In the DIVINFOOD case, the nine-grade entries for each of the four attributes made it possible to identify statistically significant differences and interactions between demographic categories and attributes. Responses to open question to add a word describing the taste could be illustrated in word clouds.

The figure 1 below shows an example of how results from the hedonic nine-grade liking scale can be presented.

A methodological reflection is that if the tasting is performed at a multilingual event (e.g. with participants from different countries), one needs to be aware of risks of misunderstandings or misinterpretations of questions and answers. Another learning is that several participants considered some of the pea varieties as hard, reflecting the challenge to reach similar hardness depending on optimal cooking time for each variety. Handling this might require additional pre-boiling tests to ensure similar hardness between the varieties.

A final and important methodological remark refers to sample randomisation. To handle many samples and collect data without the risk of confusion, the same order of samples was used for all participants. But the taste and sensory impression of any given sample might also be influenced by the impression of the previous sample. To avoid bias in the evaluation and comparison of different samples, the order in which participants taste different samples should therefore be randomized – this is commonly required for publishing the results in a scientific article. One must therefore consider the trade-off between efficiency (number of participants conducting the tasting within a certain time) and scientific rigor when planning and performing the tasting.

Figure 1. Score distribution (n=71) for the liking of taste and texture for each of the four pea varieties tested at the Copenhagen plant food festival. Each colour represents one pea variety, and all participants tasted the peas in the same order (1 pink, 2 green, 3 blue, 4 purple)

5.3.5 Good practices for implementing a community-based consumer evaluation with cooking and tasting at home

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
ACC, Ömki, Agri Kulti	Consumer evaluation with cooking and tasting at home	Trained staff	Overall liking assessment of innovative food products	€	<p>It is important to increase the testers' knowledge on NUCs, so they had to participate in a webinar before the product test</p> <p>Promote the community evaluation through social media, in newspapers, at events</p> <p>To support consumers in the challenge, send emails with recipes and advice on the use of the selected NUCs</p> <p>Distribute a preliminary questionnaire to understand the consumers' dietary preferences, habits and to collect statistical data</p> <p>After the evaluation period send a follow-up questionnaire to participants to understand changes in consumers' habits in the long-term.</p>

ACC organised three community-based consumer evaluation with cooking and tasting at home, in collaboration with ÖMKI and Agri Kulti.

NUC pasta evaluation:

Species of NUC: Emmer (*Triticum turgidum* ssp. *dicoccon*), einkorn (*Triticum monococcum*) and spelt (*Triticum spelta*)

Tested recipes: Pasta based dishes

Involved actors, stakeholders: 25 consumers at their own homes, experts (researchers)

Figure 2. NUC flour community evaluation promotion and webinar

Context and methodology for quality evaluation: pasta made from ancient grains of NUCs (emmer, einkorn and spelt) were tested with consumers. It was important to increase the testers' knowledge on this topic, so they had to participate in a webinar before the product test.

Registration for the community evaluation has been widely promoted via social media, advertisements, newspaper inserts or at events. This community evaluation has been presented as a 'community challenge', enabling participants to learn about and discover NUC-based recipes

that they could cook and enjoy at home. Consumers received 4 emails containing recipes and tips on using NUC cereals. A webinar has been organised with the participation of experts. Pasta were sent by post. Participants gave their feedback on their experience via an online questionnaire. Data have been collected before and after the evaluation, both to characterise the participants and capture their food habits.

Dry legumes evaluation:

The species of NUC involved in the evaluation: Green lentils (*Lens culinaris*), split peas (*Pisum sativum*) and chickpeas (*Cicer arietinum*)

Involved actors, stakeholders: 100 consumers at their own homes, experts (including a food influencer)

Context and methodology for quality evaluation: The community-based consumer evaluation with cooking and tasting at home from legume products was organised with the name: Hello Legumes! challenge.

HELLO HÜVELYESEK! KIHÍVÁS
 Lencse, sárgaborsó, csicseriborsó és társai: csatlakozz a kihíváshoz és egy hónapon át legyenek ők a táplálkozásod sztárjai!

WEBINÁR A HÜVELYESEKRŐL:
 FEBRUÁR 5., 18:00
 ZOOM

2024.01.22.

Hello legumes! Join our February challenge!

Perhaps one of the biggest myths about vegetarian and vegan diets is that the human body does not get enough protein through them. However, this is not true at all, we can also get sufficient quantity and quality of protein from plant sources. One of the best sources of plant protein is various legumes. The first Conscious Shopper Challenge of 2024 encourages you to get to know these healthy and versatile ingredients better!

The course of the challenge

1. Register for the challenge by midnight on January 31st!
2. After registration, you will receive the webinar link to participate, and the first hundred applicants will be sent gift legume packages to the address provided during registration, containing three 25 dkg packages of green lentils, yellow peas, and chickpeas. (We only ship domestically)
3. During the four-week challenge, we will send you a newsletter every week with useful tips and recipes that you can get inspired from!
4. Experiment and share your experiences with us. Use the hashtag #hellohüvelyesek in your posts!
5. After completing the challenge, we will send you an evaluation questionnaire. If you fill out the questionnaire and send us a picture of yourself completing the challenge, we will give you a free Conscious Shopper product test of your choice. The first 70 residents of Zugló will receive an IKEA gift package thanks to the Zugló Municipality.

Figure 3. Advertisement for the Hello legumes! challenge

The same method was used (communication to recruit participants, webinar, product dispatch, online questionnaire), but two options were offered to participants: 1) trying a legume they had never used before, 2) cooking legumes for 4 weeks.

NUC flour evaluation:

Location: at the consumers' home

Species of NUC: Emmer (*Triticum turgidum ssp. dicoccon*), einkorn (*Triticum monococcum*)

Tested recipes: Flour based recipes

Involved actors, stakeholders: 396 consumers, experts (researchers, a baker)

Figure 4. NUC flour community evaluation promotion and webinar

The same method has been applied. However, due to the high number of volunteers, it was not possible to provide flour to all. Then, consumers were provided with information to buy products made with NUCs flour and take part in the evaluation (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Brochure ‘Where to buy NUC flour’ – a guide to outlets selling emmer and einkorn flour and flour-based products, sent to participants in the evaluation

5.3.6 Good practices for implementing quality assessment with restaurants and schools for chefs

DIVINFOOD partner	Technique	Who (users)	What (purpose)	Cost	Key warnings
mPmC	Recipe creation by chefs	Innovation actors	Capturing the sensory qualities of NUCs through their processing by chefs	€	Recruit a wide range of chefs and cooking schools to gather different opinions and help ensure that chefs of all kinds can embrace the NUC in the future Provide the chef with the NUC in a form suitable for them (e.g. whole or as flour) Capture the sensory quality during the creation of the recipe

Chefs’ assessment of a product’s sensory quality is important for building the reputation of little-known plant species such as the NUCs studied in DIVINFOOD. Chefs are key influencers in food

consumption. Developing a recipe inherently involves the ability to evoke sensory appeal (taste, texture, appearance, smell). The creation of a recipe reveals the sensory quality of an ingredient, whether it is high or low. To appreciate the quality of a NUC, it must play a central role in the recipe.

The main challenge is to interest chefs in a NUC about which little is known. While this lack of knowledge could be a drawback, it can become an attraction for the chefs. It has to be turned into a professional challenge, allowing them to showcase their creativity in recipe development and reminding them of Jean Anthelme Brillat-Savarin's aphorism in *The Physiology of Taste* (1826): "The discovery of a new dish does more for human happiness than the discovery of a new star", a saying they all had to learn in culinary school. Information about the history of NUC or its nutritional properties is also useful for persuading chefs to give it a try.

To capture the sensory profile of a NUC as appreciated by chefs, it requires convincing and involving chefs from various culinary backgrounds, haute cuisine chefs, local restaurant chefs, sandwich shop chefs, catering chefs, pastry chefs as well as students in culinary schools. Recipes from appetisers to desserts with the NUC have to be encouraged, exploring the possibility of integrating it into future menus or desserts.

The sensory qualities and flaws of the NUC, as described by the chefs, should be noted down, either by the person conducting the study or by the chef themselves, ideally whilst preparing the recipe.

6. Conclusion

These guidelines present a concise framework for assessing food and raw material quality across three key dimensions: nutritional, sensorial and safety. Drawing on DIVINFOOD partners' experience, they bring together a wide range of methods to support integrated quality evaluation of diversified plant-based products by both established and emerging actors.

Some approaches, particularly for nutritional assessment, require specialised laboratory expertise, dedicated equipment and higher analytical costs. Others, especially several organoleptic evaluations, can be implemented by small-scale companies, civil-society organisations or non-trained participants, with minimal equipment and limited cost, while still generating highly informative results.

Collaborative settings such as living labs offer an effective way to share capacities, whereby academic or technical partners provide methodological know-how and access to equipment for actors who lack such resources. These guidelines aim to encourage and structure such collaborations so that all three quality dimensions can be adequately covered when new, especially NUC-based, foods or ingredients are developed, supporting their entry to the market as nutritionally appropriate, sensorially acceptable and safe products.

